

Action Plan Based on the Factors in Studying at CDSGA as Perceived by the College Freshmen A.Y. 2021-2022

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine the factors in studying at CDSGA as perceived by the college freshmen A.Y. 2021-2022 and to formulate an action plan to improve the quality services of CDSGA based on the result gathered.

It is a quantitative research method using descriptive and inferential statistics to answer the research problems. The percentage was computed to answer problems 1, 2, and 3. The Chi² was computed to answer problem 4.

The findings showed that the majority of the college freshmen students are from CDSGA and other schools outside the City of San Jose del Monte Bulacan got 10.2%. The major source of knowing CDSGA is Facebook which got 35.71%. The major reason the respondents chose to study at CDSGA is Quality which got 43.88%. There was no statistically significant relationship between School Last Attended and Source of Knowing CDSGA.

An action plan was formulated based on the findings of the study on the factors of studying at CDSGA as perceived by the college freshmen A.Y. 2021-2022.

Keywords: Action Plan, CDSGA, College Freshmen, Facebook, Factors in Studying, Quality, Quality Service.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to UNESCO Institute for Statistics that 96.29% of adult population aged 15 years and above in the Philippines are able to read and write while about 2,724,396 adults are illiterate. This means that education is very important for the Filipinos to succeed in life. The Philippine constitution gives priority to education and the government provides free education from Kinder to Senior High School. There are also state universities and colleges subsidized by the Philippine Government that the college students can continue their tertiary level of education.

College students all over the Philippines have a choice of 112 State Colleges and Universities, 121 Local Colleges and Universities, and 1,729 Private Higher Education Institutions as of 2020.

With these large number of public and private colleges, competition is very tight among schools and colleges. In fact, there are number of private schools in the country that closed their operation amidst of the Covid-19 Pandemic.

The school administrators should consider how the students feel about various aspects of attending a certain school. The administration will then have a better understanding of how to draw in both students and other stakeholders. Additionally, it will provide a clearer picture of the school's pleasure in offering high-quality education.

In the study of Skinner (2019), it looked into the college enrollment choices made by a cohort of students who were initially enrolled in college in the middle of the 2000s and were nationally representative. When controlling for student characteristics and regional labor market conditions, he discovered that while cost, distance, and fit were still significant factors in choosing between universities, they were less significant in the decision of whether to enroll at all. He added that

students are sensitive to cost, distance, and match when applying to colleges, according to a number of empirical studies.. As a result, financial aid and expanding educational options may have a positive impact on students' educational decisions. While students who enrolled in the 1970s, 1980s, and 1990s preferred nearby, less expensive colleges when comparing colleges.

Based on Dolinsky (2010) the decision to enroll in college is likely the most significant one that most young people will have made thus far in their life. It is one that will probably influence how they live for many years to come. Given the significance of the decision to enroll in college, it is not unexpected that it has been the subject of several research studies on education. The majority of his study's findings can be conceptualized in the context of a consumer decision-making framework. Overall, the study indicated that the characteristics of academic programs, tuition costs, financial aid/scholarships, and job placement after graduation obtained the highest relevance ratings when taking into account both the male and female student sample members. The authors observe that unexpectedly, academic reputation did not receive one of the highest significance ratings.

Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel's vision is to be the leading transformational leadership institution with a unique Gabrielian Culture of Discipline, Socially Responsible, Interdependent, Functionally Productive, Godly Individuals and reaching the marginalized to thrive in the global community. With this, it strives hard to serve the majority of the poor but deserving students in the City of San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, Philippines. This research will give a clear picture to the CDSGA administration on how to make innovations to serve more students and cope with the current needs of all stakeholders.

Based from the review on research literature no study has been mentioned regarding the factors in studying at CDSGA as perceived by the college freshmen. Hence, this research is conducted.

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of this study was to determine the factors in studying at CDSGA as perceived by the college freshmen A.Y. 2021-2022.

The study sought to answer the following questions:

Problem 1. What is the school last attended by the freshmen college students of CDSGA on the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022?

Problem 2. How did the freshmen college students of CDSGA on the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022 know CDSGA?

Problem 3. What is the reason why the freshmen college students on the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022 studied at CDSGA?

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the school last attended of the freshmen college students of CDSGA on the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022 and the source of knowing CDSGA?

Problem 5. Based from the findings of the study, what Marketing Action Plan can be developed?

Null Hypothesis

This research tested one (1) null hypothesis.

H01: There is no significant relationship between the school last attended of the freshmen college students of CDSGA on the 1st Semester A.Y. 2021-2022 and the source of knowing CDSGA.

The Chi² test was used in testing the null hypothesis.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The quantitative descriptive method of research was used by the researcher in this study. The principal aim of descriptive type of research is to describe the nature and the time of study and to explore the causes of the phenomena by gathering data from the respondents.

Descriptive research is often a purposeful process in which the researcher will conduct it by means of collecting, tabulating, classifying, analyzing, and evaluating information about current situations, behaviors, attitudes, procedures, patterns, and cause-and-effect relationships, and then making adequate and precise interpretations with or without statistical methods.

The current research is concerned with the use of an effective descriptive approach to arrive at an adequate interpretation of the data, as well as the precise or appropriate use of statistical tools to determine the true meaning of the gathered data.

III. RESULTS

Summary of Findings:

The following is the summary of findings based on the problems posted in chapter 1.

1. Relative to P-1: The majority of the college freshmen students are from CDSGA and other schools outside the City of San Jose del Monte Bulacan got 10.2%.

2. Relative to P-2: The major source of knowing CDSGA is through Facebook got 35.71%.

The least of the sources of knowing CDSGA is through parents, teachers, classmates, and alumni got 1.02%.

3. Relative to P-3: The major reason for the respondents to choose to study at CDSGA is Quality which got 43.88%.

The least reasons of the respondents are late enrollee, board exam, did not passed in a state university, to have a lot of knowledge, and schedule which got 1.02%.

4. Relative to P-4: There was no statistically significant relationship between the School Last Attended and Source of Knowing CDSGA.

5. Relative to P-5: An action plan based on the factors in studying at CDSGA as perceived by the college freshmen A.Y. 2021-2022 was developed.

ACTION PLAN BASED ON THE FACTORS IN STUDYING AT CDSGA AS PERCEIVED BY THE COLLEGE FRESHMEN A.Y. 2021-2022

Problem 1						
Description	Office	Start Date	Due Date	Resources	Potential Blockers	Outcome
1. Increase awareness about CDSGA and enhance good relationship to public and private schools that are near specially those schools that do not have college programs	Marketing	September 2022	June 2023	Vehicle Flyers Incentives Social Media	Lack of Manpower Time Budget	Graduating Senior High School students will choose CDSGA as their school in college
Problem 2						
Description	Office / Personnel	Start Date	Due Date	Resources	Potential Blockers	Outcome
Strengthen postings of achievements	Marketing Zero Fee Scholars and	August 2022	July 2023	Mobile Phone Laptop	Cooperation and Consistency	Since social media is an effective

in different social media accounts of CDSGA	other Scholars of CDSGA			Internet		platform to market based on this research, a wider range of prospective clients can be reached
Organize the alumni to encourage students to study at CDSGA	OSAS Marketing	August 2022	July 2023	Meeting Space Laptop Internet	Time, availability and commitment of alumni	Alumni will promote CDSGA to prospective students. They can also share their expertise in any means to help CDSGA achieve its vision.
Problem 3						
Description	Office / Personnel	Start Date	Due Date	Resources	Potential Blockers	Outcome
Continuous quality improvement of CDSGA in all aspects of services through accreditation and research on customer satisfaction.	All teaching and non-teaching staff	August 2022	July 2023	Accreditation Documents Results of Customer Evaluation	Budget Commitment of personnel	CDSGA is a transformational leadership institution that provides quality education and an excellent client satisfaction.
Improvement of the CDSGA physical plant, facilities, laboratories, library, etc.	Administration Head for Physical Plant	August 2022	July 2023	Architectural and Engineering Plan	Budget Ongoing face to face classes	An excellent physical facilities that will support a more conducive learning environment for the students.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions:

The following are the conclusions of the study:

- 1. Relative to P-1:** Majority of the college freshmen college students came from CDSGA because of familiarity and satisfaction. Students from other schools outside the City of San Jose del Monte Bulacan choose CDSGA.
- 2. Relative to P-2:** The major source of knowing CDSGA by the freshmen college students is through social media specifically through Facebook.
- 3. Relative to P-3:** The major reason of the freshmen college students to study at CDSGA is because of quality.
- 4. Relative to P-4:** There was no statistically significant relationship between School Last Attended and Source of Knowing CDSGA.

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